

THE MAIN ROLE OF CRIMINAL LINGUISTICS IN THE FIELD OF LANGUAGE

Abdujalilova Rukhshona

Temiz branch of the Tashkent Medical Academy,
assistant of the department of Uzbek and foreign languages

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Abstract. This paper presents Forensic Linguistics (FL) as a relatively new field if it is compared to phonetics, syntax and other branches of linguistics. It is the interface between linguistics and law. It is an interdisciplinary field as it depends upon other fields like semantics, pragmatics, discourse analysis, critical discourse analysis, stylistics and phonology. The paper also proposes its history, development, importance and applications. Forensic linguistics is related to language crimes namely the crimes that are committed by means of language like bribery, perjury, conspiracy, solicitation, plagiarism and threatening.

Keywords: forensic, cybercrime, language crime, criminology, authorship identification, perjury, threatening, and solicitation.

INTRODUCTION

Law is codified in language. Indeed, without language, there is no law. Roger Shuy is of the opinion that the average person cannot read x-ray in the same way the physicians can do. Simply because the physicians are well-trained to do this. In the same manner, linguists are well trained to see and hear structures that are invisible to laymen (Shuy, 1993, p.xvii). Forensic linguistics has made important contributions to the criminal justice system.

The word 'forensic' is defined in Oxford English Dictionary as: an adjective pertaining to, connected with or used in courts of law. From this definition, it can be concluded that Forensic linguistics is an interface between language, crime and law (Khoyi et al., 2014, p.313).

Forensic linguistics, like almost all sciences, has not a specific moment at which it is possible to say it began. Scholars and many others, since the eighteenth century, had problems about the authorship of famous texts, even sacred books and Shakespeare's plays (John Olsson, 2014, p.4). Forensic Linguistics does not have an actual appearance until 1968 with the analysis of Professor Jan Svartvik (The Evans Statement: A Case for Forensic Linguistics) of statements taken by police officers at Notting hill Police Station in 1953. He was the first one to introduce the term forensic. Professor Svartvik is one of the famous linguists who worked a lot in the field of corpus linguistics, which is in turn, a systemic linguistic analysis of bulk and large bodies that are called

corpus. This work helped him to work in a scientific way, and to deal with a bulky amount of material.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Forensic Linguistics (FL) is a branch of applied linguistics which relates and links law to legal processes. In other words, it is the application of linguistics to three main areas, namely written legal texts, spoken legal practices (interactions) and provision of evidence for both civil and criminal investigations and courtroom proceedings (Coulthard, Grant and Kredens, 2011,p.529). In addition, FL involves an application of scientific linguistic knowledge to civil and criminal cases. Forensic linguists are much concerned with the language used by the police in interviews with suspects and witnesses. They are also concerned with the language of lawyers and witnesses in legal proceedings in trials, investigations and sentences (Mohsen, Sajedi and Sajedi, 2014, p.223).

Xuehua Li argues that FL is a branch of Forensic science like forensic chemistry and forensic psychology. Moreover, forensic linguists have an ethical and professional responsibility, as they provide an objective analysis to legal community with reliable information in order to prevent unfair conviction or acquittal of criminals (2011, p.529).He adds that forensic linguist is a ' a cover term for the language scientist serving as a legal expert' (ibid, p.560).For him, the forensic linguist has two tasks, i.e., to find clues and offer opinions. Clues means linguistic evidence either to the court or jury. The linguist's clues help in forming the formal opinion that is based upon theatrical knowledge and expert's experience.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Malcolm Coulthard is of opinion that Forensic Linguistics is an interdisciplinary field; it lies between the two fields: law and linguistics (p.3), whereas John Olsson argues that FL is the interface between linguistics (the science of language) and law including law enforcement (John Olsson, 2013, p.3).Language is a medium of communication among law enforcement authorities and suspect/witnesses and a medium of legal argumentations in the courtroom (Shuy, 1993, p.45).

According to Gibbons, law depends upon language to a very large extent; law is an entirely linguistic institution, i.e. laws are codified and interpreted in language. Language enables and constrains laws. Moreover, legal language is seen by many persons as difficult; it can be made simple and easy only by forensic linguists (Gibbons, 2003, p.1).

Shuy states that ordinary people are sometimes obliged to deal with legal documents, and that they find the legal language or the legalese difficult to be understood. Undoubtedly, every field has its jargon. People have the right to understand. Forensic linguists try to facilitate it or make these texts intelligible. They also help in simplifying, interpreting, explaining and formulating codes.

In the first type of interaction, Paul Grice's cooperative principle and its four maxims (1989) and Austin's theory of speech acts (1975) are very helpful and effective, according to Maite Correa. They help participants who interact to understand the techniques and intricacies of any interaction. One has to follow or obey them to have an effective communication.

Grice's Maxims are as follows:

Quality: do not say what you believe to be false or that for which you lack adequate evidence.

Quantity: make your contribution neither more nor less than is required.

Relation: be relevant.

Manner: avoid obscurity of expression and ambiguity. Be brief and orderly.

When speakers do not follow the maxims, they flout them. When a speaker flouts one or more of the maxims without deliberate intention he misleads the hearer/listener who tries to reconcile what the speaker says, assuming that the speaker is cooperating with him/her. Flouting the maxims leads the hearer/listener to infer what the speaker means. Grice calls this conversational implicature (Correa, 2013, p.5).

According to Shuy (1997, p.181), there are some techniques that are commonly used during the interrogation and in the courtroom. They are: firstly, yes/no questions which imply more control by the speaker over the hearer than the open-questions do. Secondly, tag questions and questions that presuppose facts that have not yet been established indeed involve more power in controlling evidence (ibid, p.268). The last one is promises and threats.

Forensic linguists are known as expert witness. Simply they can provide evidence and advice to help police in investigations. They can aid courts and police in authorship identification: a forensic linguist compares an anonymous text to known texts (texts that have identified authors) to decide whether they are written by the same author or not. This analysis is very effective in sms text messages, twitter feeds, and other short texts, especially

when someone is missed, supposed to be dead, but his/her mobile phone continues to send messages. Forensic linguists work as consultants to determine whether the suspect messages belong to the same author or not. Professor Malcolm Coulthard is a very good expert in this field. Sociolinguistic profiling is directly related to this application of FL.

Recently, some forensic linguists aid a police Pedophile Unit (adults who are sexually attracted to children) by analyzing and synthesizing texts to help girls to identify those whom they deal with whether they are children or not (Coulthard, 2011, p. 5).

Sociolinguistic Profiling:

Forensic linguistics draws upon many different fields of applied linguistics such as discourse analysis, critical discourse analysis, stylistics, phonetics, phonology, graphology, sociology and sociolinguistics. Sociolinguistic profiling stems from the field of sociolinguistics directly. Depending upon the concept that our linguistic performance is greatly affected by a number of social factors, namely age, educational level, gender, geographical and social class, forensic linguists can determine the author of the anonymous text, or the origin of it. Sociolinguistic profiling is needed or required when police have no strong hypotheses about the author's identity. In this case, forensic linguist searches for linguistic clues to solve the mystery of the dispute. Linguistic clues are age, gender, social and regional background of the author (Coulthard et al., 2011, p.2).

Authorship Attribution:

Forensic linguists are asked to do authorship attribution when there is a dispute on one or more texts and one or more authors. In this case, linguists search for linguistic patterns at all levels: vocabulary, syntax, grammar, semantics, punctuation and orthography. The forensic linguist is provided with text(s) of the suspect, called disputed texts, and other text(s) of known author to enable them to compare and contrast different texts. Disputed texts can be wills, threat letters, suicide notes, tweets, face book and whats app messages. It is worth-mentioning that the shorter the text, the more complicated the task. When the text is long, the discovery of distinctive features of the text or the author becomes easier. Forensic linguistic analysis makes full use of the contribution of other fields like statistics and computational linguistics. Forensic linguists make quantitative analysis of large amounts of data (ibid, p. 3).

Interactional Meaning:

Forensic linguists can identify an anonymous speaker in a phone conversation, especially those who threaten, extort, conspire and blackmail. The prominent one in this field is Professor Roger Shuy who has analyzed covert tapes used by the police to prosecute what he calls 'language crimes' (Grant, 2012,p. 179).Language crimes are those ones that are linguistic in their nature, or rather performed mainly by language like threatening, bribing, extorting and conspiring. Language crimes are discussed later in this paper.

Determining Meaning:

Forensic linguist provides interpretation of legal texts. S/he can provide meaning of slang or ambiguous words. S/he is asked to introduce evidence in the cases of disputed meaning like meaning in contracts to determine whether particular phrases constitute a threat or a defamation.

Forensic linguistic evidence is needed in cybercrime i.e. those that refer to crimes committed on line, using common technologies as computers, internet and smart phones. These crimes also include hatred crimes, libel and fraud. They may be traditional crimes like theft but using internet.

Trade Mark Disputes and Copyright Infringement:

Forensic linguists can provide help not only in criminal investigations but in civil cases, as well. They can work as experts in trade mark disputes and copyright problems, most successfully, plagiarism detection.

Forensic Phonetics:

It is used to identify speaker through his/her accent, pronunciation, regional background. It helps in determining similarities and differences among speakers through analyzing recorded tapes. It is worth-mentioning that there are intra-author and inter-author variations.Intra-author means the ways in which the author's text differs from other author's texts, while inter- author refers to the ways the different texts of different authors differ from each other.

Language Crimes:

Simply, criminology is the science that studies crime: its creation, development, and prevention. Crime is examined through law and other sciences like psychology, sociology, biology and medicine. It is an applied science.it is not a closed science (Momeni, 2011, p.733). It needs experts from different fields. Crimes are committed in different forms and different ways. Nowadays, some forms of crimes are committed in internet. This necessitates the help of internet experts. Actually, it is difficult to have a comprehensive and acceptable definition of criminology.

Shuy presents a table that explains the main differences and similarities among different language crimes.

	Threatening	Warning	Advising	Promising
To the speaker's benefit	X			
To the hearer's benefit		X	x	X
To the hearer's detriment	X			
From the speaker's perspective	X	X		X
From the hearer's perspective			X	
Speaker controls outcome	X			
Hearer controls outcome	X		x	

Shuy develops a new concept that he calls **conversational contamination**. He emphasizes its importance in stating whether the person committed the language crime or not.

CONCLUSION

Olsson is of the opinion that lawyers and forensic linguists should cooperate with each other in the interests of justice. He adds that it is the task of linguists to widen their understanding of international laws, issues of international human rights, and the relationship between law and language across the globe (Olsson, 2014, p.1).

FL has a promising future, the researcher hopes to be applied in Egyptian courts and legal system, as it provides an objective and impartial linguistic evidence.

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